

Combining miRNA regulation and Sleeping Beauty System For Liver Cancer Treatment

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Abstract:

miRNAs can regulate multiple genetic and epigenetic events simultaneously, and miR-122 serves as a potent nucleic acid medicine to treat liver cancer. Successful miRNA therapy requires suitable delivery systems with high specificity, high efficiency and long term expression of therapeutic miR-NAs. However, in vivo nanoparticle administration inevitably results in nucleic acid entry into non-hepatocyte cells, leading to leaky miRNA expression gene and possible toxicity. It also has a problem with short effect time. To improve safety and efficiency, we generated a novel miRNA therapy. We built a switch that exploits the Sleeping Beauty (SB) transposon based system signature in hepatocytes. We first revealed that miR-200c and miR-126 are particularly expressed in normal lung cell and vein endothelial cell and lowly expressed in liver cancer cell, respectively, which allowed us to engineer a switch based on distinct miRNA expression signature, namely miRNA binding site technique. We have developed SB based system to enable hepatic specific and long term expression of therapeutic miR-122, and then incorporated the entire device into a single plasmid. We next validated the function of our plasmid in vitro. Finally, we evaluated the antitumor effects after systemic administration of therapeutic SB vectors expressing miR-122 loaded in nanoparticle in the liver cancer models. We expect that this highly efficient and specific miRNA delivery system can serve as a potent anti-tumor therapeutic modality and a translational platform for clinical applications.

Keywords:

Liver cancer, miR-122, gene therapy, synthetic biology, nanoparticle

Figure 1: Schematic illustration showing the miRNA-switch based therapeutic strategy to suppress hepatocellular carcinoma and avoid the side.

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PVA-microencapsulation: effective drug delivery system to inhibit epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT) in-vitro.

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Abstract:

Introduction:

Anchorage independent cell growth followed by tumorigenicity is the key factor for epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT). Tumor cell spreading or metastasis occurs when carcinogen induced epithelial tumor cell mutated CDH1 gene present in chromosome 16q22. Down regulation of CDH1 gene inactivate phenotypic expression of Ecadherin. Hence tumor cell loses cell to cell adhesion and cell-matrix adhesion mediated by integrin. Microencapsulation is the powerful techniques for entrapment of the hydrophobic drug into hydrophilic polymeric micelles. In our experiment we prepared a PVA microencapsulation loaded with single hydrophobic compound (having anticancer property) extracted from *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract. Therefore our research work has been designed to evaluate EMT inhibition corresponded to the anti-metastatic activity of this drug loaded delivery system.

Methodology:

The purified drug loaded PVA microencapsulation was prepared by one step modified binary nonsolvent co-solvation: phase separation method with loading efficiency of 68% mean value (n=3). It is then characterized by SEM, TEM and FTIR. EMT inhibition corresponded to anti-metastatic activity was evaluated by cell based adhesion assay, soft agar assay followed by caspase induced immunoblotting assay for mechanism and pathways analysis on both MCF-7 (Epithelial) and MDA-MB-231 (Mesenchymal) cell line.

Result:

Chemical group analysis of the purified compounds loaded delivery system shows that the purified compound may entrap into the PVA-microencapsulation. Presence of the N=C=S group at nearly 2000 cm⁻¹ and The transmission band near 1500 cm⁻¹ indicates presence of aromatic group and benzene ring within the delivery matrix. On comparing the FTIR of purified compounds, its intensity decreases, indicating entrapment of the compound into embryonic core polymer. SEM and TEM analysis indicate roughly spherical submicron particle embedded in polymer bed (Fig: 01). pH dependent swelling property indicate that the maximum drug release occurs in acidic pH at 7 min (approx).

Figure 1: SEM analysis of the PVA microencapsulation

In adhesion assay 62% MCF-7 and nearly 40% MDA-MB-231 cells were adhering in Gelatin fibronectin (GF) coated plate. The initial proliferation rate was very slow in both cell lines. MDA-MB-231 cell line started to proliferate earlier than MCF-7 but rate of proliferation was higher in MCF-7 in comparison of MDA-MB-231. On treatment, MDA-MB-231 cell line is inhibited more than MCF-7 cell line. Proliferation rate is also decreased in the similar way. Therefore epithelial cell have greater affinity to substratum against mesenchymal cell.

Conclusion:

PVA-microencapsulation system is more effective in delivering the drug in target tissue with less time and but in higher efficiency compare to non-encapsulated system as reflected through results of drug loading efficiency and pH dependent release efficiency. Hence this encapsulated system may increase bioavailability. Therefore drug delivery system showed anti-metastatic activity may be through altering the CDH1 gene mediated E-cadherin expression.

Keywords:

PVA-microencapsulation, Anti-metastatic, Drug delivery system, EMT-inhibition.

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Quercetin inhibits Caco-2 colorectal cancer cell angiogenesis through the role of NF- κ B p65 and VEGFR2

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Abstract:

Colorectal cancer (CRC) aggressiveness caused by cancer angiogenesis, processes of new blood vessels formation, occurs after releasing of proangiogenic factors from growing cancer. VEGFR2, VEGFA specific receptor, has major roles in cancer angiogenesis which can be activated through various mechanisms including NF- κ B activation. By NF- κ B activation could lead to various important cellular activities involved in angiogenesis processes. Quercetin, flavonoid compound found in fruits and vegetables, was reported as an anti-cancer agent in carcinogenesis, cancer proliferation and angiogenesis in various types of cancers including CRC. However, the communication mechanisms between sromal cancer cells is still unclear. Studying the effects of quercetin in inhibiting CRC cell angiogenesis through the role of NF- κ B and VEGFR2 would provide more information. Determining effect of quercetin in in vitro tube formation of HUVECs was done by tubulogenesis assay with 24 h treated Caco-2 cells with 5 and 10 μ g/ml quercetin as condition medium. Then determining effect of quercetin in NF- κ B p65 and VEGFR2 protein expression in HUVECs was done after cultured them with 10 μ g/ml quercetin treated Caco-2 cells by using indirect immunofluorescence assay. The results of tubulogenesis assay, total tube length per area of HUVECs were significantly decreased at $p < 0.005$ compared with non-treated group in dose dependent manner. Also, fluorescence intensities of NF- κ B p65 and VEGFR2 expression were significantly decreased at $p < 0.005$ compared with non treated group after analyzed by ImageJ program. In conclusion, quercetin inhibits Caco-2 cells induced angiogenesis related suppressing an activated NF- κ B and VEGFR2 expressions in HUVECs. (Figure 1) But the certain mechanisms are still unclear. However, this makes quercetin can be used as an ant angiogenesis agent in CRC treatment with less adverse effects.

Keywords:

Colorectal cancer, angiogenesis, quercetin, NF- κ B p65, VEGFR2

Figure 1: Figure demonstrating inhibitory effects of quercetin in Caco-2 cells-induced angiogenesis through suppressing NF- κ B p65 and VEGFR2 expression in HUVECs. References: 1. Judah, F. (2002), Role of angiogenesis in tumor growth and metastasis, *Seminars in Oncology*, 29(6), 15-18. 2. Sam, T., Jerome, C., Yannick, V., et, at. (2017) The role of Nuclear Factor-kappa B signaling in human cervical cancer, *Clin. Rev. in Oncology/Hematology*, 120, 141150. 3. Wei, S., Xiaofei, Z., Jiarui, X., Han, Z. (2017), Quercetin inhibits angiogenesismediated human retinoblastoma growth by targeting vascular endothelial growth factor receptor, *Oncology letters*, 14, 3343-3348.

Photodynamic therapy with purpurin 18 on breast cancer

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Abstract:

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a promising treatment in oncology and has been proved to be efficient in clinic. Photosensitizer, as the key element in PDT, could be preferentially accumulated in tumor sites. After activation with specific light, photosensitizer could generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can induce cell death of tumor cells. We investigated the effect of purpurin 18 (pu 18) (Figure 1A) on breast cancer both in vitro and in vivo and further explored the underlying mechanism. Pu 18 combined with 630nm light irradiation has very efficient photodynamic effect on breast cancer.

Totally, experiments were divided into four groups: sham control, light treatment alone, pu 18 treatment alone, and the combined treatment of pu 18 with light (PDT group). In vitro study showed that on MCF-7 breast cancer cells, pu 18 majorly gathered at mitochondria and endoplasmic reticulum. After the illumination of light, a low dosage of pu 18 could generate ROS (Figure 1B) to significantly destroy the mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) (Figure 2A) and elevate the intracellular calcium level, then eventually induce cell cytotoxicity (Figure 2B). On triple negative breast cancer 4T1 cells, pu 18 majorly accumulated at lysosome. The damage induced by PDT could transfer to mitochondria, resulting in a dissipated MMP, and finally induce apoptosis of 4T1 cells. What's more, it was proved that PDT could destroy the structure and inhibit the growth of MCF-7 and 4T1 3D spheroids. The in vivo study animal model was built by injecting 4T1 cells into axillary of Balb/c mice. After 3 times of PDT, the tumour volume and weight were significantly inhibited comparing with other 3 groups, about 60% (Figure 3), without influencing histological and functional impairment of major organs. And PDT with pu 18 could prolong the survival rate of mice and inhibit the pulmonary metastasis of 4T1 cells, showing its promising value.

Keywords:

Purpurin 18, breast cancer, photodynamic therapy, mitochondrial membrane potential, intracellular calcium, apoptosis.

Figure 1: Structure of purpurin 18 (A) and the yield of ROS in MCF-7 cells (B).

Figure 2: The MMP analysis (A) and apoptosis (B) of MCF-7 cells in different groups.

Figure 2: The tumor volume (A) and weight (B) in mice model of different groups. **P < 0.05.

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Prediction of HCC using Hepatic Fibrosis scores and a Novel Non Invasive score: A Retrospective Egyptian Study on 2363 Patients

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Abstract:

Background and Aims:

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is believed to be one of the most challenging tumours with rising incidence, prevalence and mortality rates. Egypt is responsible for almost cases of HCC in Africa. Meanwhile the latest decade, a considerable increase was observed among Egyptian patients with chronic liver disease related HCC (from 4.0% to 7.2%). The risk of hepatocarcinogenesis depends on background liver factors, of which fibrosis is a major determinant. Serum markers and developed scores are of increasing importance in non-invasive diagnosis of hepatic fibrosis. Because the fibrosis indices correlate with liver fibrosis, it was presumed that these indices could be closely related to HCC development. In the current study, we aimed to evaluate the inflammatory and fibrosis markers as predictors for HCC development among patients with chronic liver disease. Moreover, we developed a score based on routinely available, simple, non-invasive parameters for early diagnosis of HCC. We also tested its accuracy in HCC detection in comparison to the widely used tumour marker “AFP”

Method:

A retrospective study included 1291 HCC Egyptian patients recruited from the multidisciplinary HCC clinic, Kasr Al-Ainy hospital, Faculty of medicine, Cairo University in the period and 1072 naïve chronic hepatitis C patients with advanced fibrosis (\geq F3) and cirrhosis (F4). Serum fibrosis scores were calculated for these p[patients; King, Fibro Q, Aspartate aminotransferase-to-platelet ratio index (APRI), AST to ALT ratio (AAR), LOK, Goteborg University Cirrhosis Index (GUCI), Fibro alpha and BRC scores were calculated for all patients. Regression analysis and receiver-operator curves were plotted to assess the sensitivity, specificity and predictive values for the significant scores with the best cut-off for predicting HCC.

Results:

HCC patients were significantly older 57.83 ± 7.51 years than non HCC patients 48.24 ± 8.27 years ($p < 0.001$). They also showed significant

Thrombocytopenia, hyperbilirubinemia, elevated serum AST and AFP serum levels. Serum albumin was significantly lower in HCC patients.

Regarding the fibrosis scores, there was highly significant difference between the HCC and non HCC patients in all calculated scores ($P=0.0001$).

On multivariate analysis, we found that old age, male gender, low serum, albumin and high AFP were independently associated with HCC development. The overall formula that could best predict HCC was then constructed by stepwise logistic regression modelling.

Hepatocellular Carcinoma Multidisciplinary clinic – Cairo University

(HMC-CU):

Logit probability of HCC = $2.524 + 0.152 \times \text{age} - 0.121 \times \text{Hb} - 0.696 \times \text{INR} -$

$1.059 \times \text{Alb} + 0.022 \times \text{AFP} + 0.976 \times \text{Gender}$

Gender: Male=1 ; Female= 0

At a cut-off point of 0.5, HMC-CU enabled the correct identification of patients with HCC with 90% sensitivity, 80.6% specificity. AUC was 0.93 and the 95% confidence interval was 0.917 - 0.94. While serum AFP was able to

Diagnose HCC at cut-off value of 10.05 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ at sensitivity of 70% and specificity of 61%. AUC was 0.76 and the 95% confidence interval was 0.74 - 0.78

Conclusion:

HMC-CU could be helpful for early diagnosis of HCC. It could be used worldwide without imposing extra cost for sophisticated tests.

The elegance of our score is based on its simplicity, being based on routine laboratory parameters and serum AFP which is being used for screening of patients in many centres all over the world

Biography:

Dalia Omran is currently working as a Assistant professor of endemic hepatogastreterology & infectious diseases Department of Medicine of Endemic Medicine and Hepatology at Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.

Luteolin Induces Apoptosis in Tamoxifen-Resistant Breast Cancer Cell Through the Regulation of H3K4 Monomethylation and PI3K/AKT/mTOR Pathway

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Abstract:

Breast cancer is one of the common cancers in woman, and about 70% of breast cancer expresses the estrogen receptor (ER) gene. The receptor-mediated signal transduction pathways stimulate the proliferation and growth of mammary gland cells. For ER-positive (ER+) breast cancer patients, endocrine therapy is used as the first choice for the clinical strategy. Tamoxifen as adjuvant therapy is the most commonly used for anti-estrogen. However, drug resistance often occurs in ER+ breast cancer patients, which is either de-novo resistance or acquired resistance. It causes the recurrence and higher metastatic activity of ER+ breast cancer and reduces the lifespan of patients. It is an important clinical problem that needs to overcome tamoxifen resistance. Luteolin, a common flavonoid, possesses anti-inflammatory and anti-tumor activities. Here we explored the function of luteolin act as adjuvant treatment in tamoxifen-resistant ER+ breast cancer. In this study, we reported that luteolin reduced cell viability of tamoxifen-resistant ER+ breast cancer (MCF7-TamR) cells, and luteolin inhibited cell proliferation, and induced apoptosis, cell cycle arrest and also caused mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) dysfunction in MCF7-TamR cells. In the wound healing assay, the combination of luteolin and tamoxifen inhibited motility ability of MCF7-R cells. Furthermore, the activity of proteins related to PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, such as PI3K, Akt, and mTOR, were decreased. Moreover, the expression of P27 that related to the cell cycle was increased in luteolin-treated MCF7-TamR cells. Combinational treatments of luteolin and lower doses of PI3K/Akt/mTOR inhibitors were performed in MCF7-TamR cells and the synergistically inhibition on cell viability of MCF7-TamR cells was found. Besides, the histone methylation had been known that it plays an essential role as suppressor in cell proliferation through the regulation of gene expression. We also found that mono methylation of Histone 3 Lysine 4 (H3K4) and methyl-transferase for H3K4me1, MLL3, were increased in the luteolin-treated MCF7-TamR cells. Taken together, our finding showed that luteolin inhibited proliferation and induced apoptosis through the regulation of PI3K/Akt pathway in MCF7 TamR cells and combination of luteolin and PI3K/Akt inhibitors had a synergistic inhibitory effect on cell viability. On the other hand, we also found that luteolin promoted monomethylation of H3K4 and reduced the gene expression of Ras, the activator of PI3K, in MCF7-TamR cells. The crosslink with H3K4 methylation and PI3K/Akt pathway through regulation of Ras expression in MCF7-TamR cells under luteolin treatment will be clarified further in the future.

Keywords:

Estrogen receptor positive breast cancer, tamoxifen resistant, luteolin, PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway, H3K4 monomethylation, Ras

Figure 1: The effect of luteolin on the cell viability of MCF7-TamR cells. (A) The compound structure of luteolin. (B) Luteolin repressed cell viability of MCF7-TamR cells. (C) The effect of luteolin combined with Akt inhibitor in MCF7-TamR cells. (D) The effect of luteolin combined with mTOR inhibitor in MCF7-TamR cells.

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Aloe Emodin-Induced Cell Death in Triple Negative Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract:

Triple-negative breast cancers (TNBC) have a higher rate of disease recurrence and distant metastasis and poorer prognosis. It is more difficult to treat TNBC than other breast cancer subtypes due to no ideal treating target. Aloe-emodin (AE), a natural compound from the rhizome of *Rheum palmatum*, has broad bioactivity, such as antitumor, antiviral, antioxidant, antibacterial activities, etc. However, AE-related research in breast cancer is limited, especially in TNBC. The human TNBC cell line MDA-MB-231 was used for this study. The effects of AE, including cell growth, cell proliferation, apoptosis, autophagy, and cell cycle, on MDA-MB-231 were determined. In addition, changes of protein expression in the possible regulation mechanisms were also investigated. AE inhibited cell growth of MDA-MB-231 and triple-positive BT-474 cells in a dose-dependent manner, whereas MDA-MB-231 cells were more sensitive to AE. The colony formation assay showed that AE could inhibit MDA-MB-231 cell proliferation. AE treatment significantly resulted in G2/M phase arrest and apoptosis through downregulation of CDK1, cyclin B1, and CDC25c and activation of procaspases 3 and 9. Furthermore, AE caused autophagy by upregulating Atg7 and Atg12 and converting LC3-I to LC3-II. The results revealed the inhibitory effects of AE on MDA-MB-231, including cell cycle arrest, apoptosis, and autophagy, suggesting that AE have clinical potential to treat triple-negative breast cancers. However, in vivo experiments are also necessary to demonstrate the efficacy of AE in TNBC.

Keywords:

Aloe emodin, Triple negative breast cancer cells, cell cycle, autophagy.

Figure 1: The effect of aloe emodin (AE) on MDA-MB-231 cells. (A) MDA-MB-231 and BT-474 cells were treated with indicated concentrations of AE for 24,48,72 h, after which the cell viability was measured using MTT assay.(B) MDA-MB-231 cells were seeded in 12-well plates at 500 cells/well. After the cells were treated with AE at the indicated doses for 48h. Then, the cells were changed with fresh media for every 2-3 days. After 2 weeks, cells were fixed, stained and photographed. Significance compared with 0 (control), *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001.

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Autophagy markers for early diagnosis of hepatocellular Carcinoma

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Abstract:

Autophagy plays an important role in the pathogenesis of many diseases such as liver diseases¹. However, the exact part it plays remains unclear. We investigated the mRNA expression levels of Beclin-1 (autophagy component), proapoptotic components (Bad, Bax), and antiapoptotic components (Bcl-2, Bcl-xL) in venous blood samples drawn from hepatitis C virus (HCV) genotype 4 infected patients with or without hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC)². The study included 30 healthy people (control group), 100 chronic hepatitis C patients (chronic hepatitis group), and 47 chronic hepatitis C patients with HCC (HCC group). qPCR was used to measure mRNA expression levels in the samples. Beclin-1, and Bad mRNA expression levels were significantly lower in the HCC group than in the chronic hepatitis and control groups ($P < 0.01$), while Bcl-2, and Bcl-xL mRNA expression levels were significantly higher ($P = 0.04$; $P < 0.01$ respectively). Autophagic markers can be used as possible biomarkers and may contribute to the development of a novel therapeutic approach.

Keywords:

Autophagy, Hepatocellular carcinoma, Hepatitis C virus, Beclin-1, Bcl-2, Bcl-xL, Bad, Bax

Figure 1: ROC curve used to determine the cut-off values of Beclin-1 and the other autophagic markers for HCC prognosis [stages 2 and 3]

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